

Cultural artefacts and mathematics: Connecting home and school

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Cultural artefacts are anything constructed by people within a group that reflects the cultural identity of that group of people. A culturally contextual teaching and learning approach supports learners by engaging them in an investigation of a topic in a cultural setting. In this study, four mathematics teachers and thirty-two students from grade six to ten participated. Students were provided a rich environment to explore mathematical ideas embedded in cultural artifacts found in the out-of-school environment. The mathematical ideas embedded in these cultural artifacts enabled students to develop mathematical ideas beyond the four walls of the classroom. Both teachers and students reported that the cultural artefacts facilitate an opportunity to explore mathematical ideas in a cultural setting and helped them to connect mathematical ideas located in the out-of-school environment with formal mathematics.

Introduction

Cultural artefacts are any object created by the people of any cultural group. These artefacts reflect the cultural identity of those groups of people. There are different types of cultural artefacts including dresses, houses, utensils, baskets, ornaments, paintings, designs, and so on. All these artefacts give information about the culture of their creators and the ideas associated with these objects (Pradhan, 2020). The study of cultural artefacts and the ethnomathematical ideas embedded in them are the sources for mathematics teaching and learning. Cultural artefacts provide rich opportunities to connect ethnomathematical ideas to the school curriculum. The pedagogy which inculcates the ideas, knowledge and experience of a certain group of people, who create different cultural artefacts that tends to preserve their social and cultural identity is called ethnopedagogy. Thus, the culturally contextualized pedagogy allows students to learn the mathematical ideas and knowledge of that time from the perspective of that particular group. Bonotto (2007) viewed that “the connection between real-world and classroom mathematics is not easy because the two contexts differ significantly” (p. 187). However, mathematics teaching and learning could be more interesting and effective if an appropriate connection is made between students’ out-of-school activities and experiences and school mathematics. The connection with students’ everyday activities and experiences seem to be more appropriate. It is widely acknowledged that the inclusion of ethnomathematical perspectives in school mathematics values students’ cultural backgrounds and experiences. The observation of mathematical ideas embedded in

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different cultural artefacts located in the surroundings of students' cultural contexts would motivate students to see mathematics as relevant to their lives outside the classroom (Adam, 2004).

Students construct mathematical knowledge with the help of their prior knowledge, experience, and active participation in their environmental activities. The cultural activities of the children include many implicit mathematical ideas. These activities provide an opportunity to connect mathematical ideas embedded in the out-of-school contexts with school mathematics lesson. Francois, Mafra, Fantinato and Vandendriessche (2018) highlighted that the integration of learners' out-of-school knowledge is a stepping-stone for acquiring new knowledge. However, in Nepal, our school mathematics curriculum and teacher training are largely ignoring learners' cultural activities and their ethnomathematical ideas (Pradhan, 2017; Ezeif, 2002). This is not only an issue with in Nepal, since Rosa and Gavarrete (2017) also observe that children's ethnomathematical knowledge and learning approaches are not taken into consideration in the formal school mathematics curricula. The mathematical ideas embedded in cultural artefacts and students' experiences should be blended with formal mathematics in the classroom. In this paper, I explore the mathematical ideas and knowledge embedded in cultural artefacts and in doing so address the following research questions.

- What mathematical ideas and knowledge are embedded in cultural artefacts?
- How might the mathematical ideas embedded in cultural artefacts be connected and used to understand school mathematics?

Framework for connecting home and school

It is now well understood that each student brings a unique set of knowledge, skills, and experiences to a new learning situation. Various research has identified that cultural artefacts and embedded ethnomathematical ideas help learners to develop formal mathematical ideas and knowledge (Pradhan, 2020). Paulo Freire (1970) suggested that “children cultural capital, the knowledge children bring to school from their home and cultural environment, should be welcomed and utilized in school for teaching and knowledge building process” (as cited in Stringer, Christensen & Baldwin, 2010, p. 24). In this way, students' out-of-school knowledge embedded in different cultural artefacts is celebrated and utilized as a pedagogical tool in the construction of mathematical meaning.

Constructivism is a widely supported educational theory that rests on the idea that students create their knowledge in the context of their own experiences (Fosnot, 1996). It focuses on students, being actively engaged in doing rather than passively engaged in receiving knowledge. The development of student's ability to construct knowledge requires apprenticeship into culturally specific cognitive and social practices. The cognitive development of a child's increasing mastery over the culturally determined developmental tasks is mediated by social agents. Vygotsky (1978) argued that an understanding of how knowledge develops requires an understanding of the social and historical origins of

knowledge and changes in that knowledge. Vygotsky (1978) metaphorically described the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) as the difference between a child's performance and that child's performance when guided by experts. This framework argues that learners are actively engaged in an activity when they are based on their interest, constructive investigation, and collaborative learning. Learners acquire knowledge about their culture and history from their encounters with adults and peers.

The framework developed in this study shows how the cultural artefacts and ethnomathematical ideas observed in children's out-of-school contexts can be a mediating tool to construct mathematical meaning. My argument in this study is that the cultural context in which children are situated is a rich environment to generate and distribute mathematical knowledge. Therefore, cultural artefacts are the background knowledge for the learner to develop foreground knowledge (Vithal & Skovsmose, 1997), a series of mathematical concepts and ideas to be perceived. In view of this, Lakoff and Nunez (2000) also considered children familiar context and experience to be the source knowledge for the development of abstract concepts (target knowledge) of mathematics. If the cultural artefacts found in the out-of-school environment are seriously observed, the learners can unfold various mathematical ideas and knowledge hidden in cultural artefacts. My framework in this study argues that ethnomathematical ideas embedded in the cultural artefacts helps to foster school mathematical knowledge in effective and meaningful ways.

Methodology for connecting home and school

My research observed the ethnomathematical ideas and knowledge embedded in cultural artefacts. In order to make a plan to approach data recording before entering the field, I prepared interview guidelines and observation protocols for teachers and students so that it would be easier for me to generate the data where in the field (Creswell, 2014). I collected data through examining documents, observing behavior, and interviewing participants both students and teachers. I carefully recorded all possible conversations with the help of the video camera and took field notes as much as I could. The data generated with the students' communities reflect how they are rich in ethnomathematical ideas and knowledge. In my study, the cultural artefacts in the students' community and their ways of understanding the natural phenomena, and their ethnomathematical knowledge were analyzed using the notion of pluralism. While conducting this research, I continuously addressed the research questions exploring the mathematical ideas embedded in the cultural artefacts and their use in teaching and learning school mathematics. The following procedure was adopted to connect the mathematical ideas and knowledge embedded in cultural artefacts to formal school mathematics.

Selection of Study Location: One of teacher participants of my study and I together visited some temples before selecting the study location where we observed the possibilities for incorporation in a mathematics lesson. Ultimately, we decided on Old Guheshwory temple situated at Tarakeshwor Municipality of Kathmandu District as the study location for the

field trip. The temple, Old Guheshwory, is a prehistoric temple established centuries ago. There are many monuments and artefacts present in and around the temple.

Selection of Student Participants: Thirty-two students were selected for this study. Out of them, eight students were selected from each grade of 6 to 8 (basic level) and four students were selected from grade 9 and 10 (secondary level) each. The student participants of this study were selected from a secondary public school of Kathmandu District.

Student Awareness Program (SAP) for Field Trip: Before the visit to the study location, the researcher presented the possibilities of mathematical ideas embedded in the cultural artefacts and encouraged them to explore. I had designed the SAP intending to encourage them to connect real-life situations and school mathematics. The SAP was conducted before going on the field trip and lasted about one hour. The thirty-two students and four mathematics teachers participated in this program.

Formation of Collaborative Group: Thirty-two students were divided into four different groups. Each group included 8 members from five different grades: 2 students from grade 6 to 8 each and one from 9 and 10. The group thus formed was heterogeneous and this provided an opportunity for collaborative learning. The group was formed in such a way that they represented students from all grade levels with the aim of providing a collaborative learning environment. Four teachers were assigned to facilitate each group.

Study Tools and Materials: Students were encouraged to explore mathematical ideas through observation of different artefacts surrounding the temple. They were provided measuring tape, paper, pencil, and other instruments by which they would explore and verify different mathematical properties. Students were also requested to write down their feelings and perceptions of the field trip, focusing on the mathematical ideas learned and the ways of gaining knowledge through the ethnopedagogy.

Lesson Design for the Field-trip: After reaching the study location, the students were first provided a common task. All the students were requested to observe different cultural artefacts surrounding the temple and note the mathematical objects they could identify. The teachers' role was to develop a lesson, monitor and provide feedback when students were engaged in the task. I along with the teachers, had to develop the tasks for the four groups of students after viewing the scenario in the temple premises. Four major open-ended tasks were: to identify a center of the circle, to identify a type of quadrilateral by measuring the sides of the terrace, to explore the concept of symmetry, and to identify an axis of reflection. Then the designed tasks were given to each group.

Data Management: This study was based on primary data collected through the observation of cultural artefacts and monuments, interviews with teachers and students. I reviewed all of the data gathered from the multiple sources (Creswell, 2014) and then organized them into categories or themes that cut across all of the data sources. After observing the data, I linked them with many possible theories to interpret them. I triangulated the data, and the theoretical closures and gave meaning to my findings.

Maintaining Ethical Issues: I ensured anonymity and confidentiality to all research participants and briefed them on how the data were going to be used and protected. As my study was intended to explore mathematical ideas of cultural artefacts embedded in the temple, it was ensured that the cultural and religious identity of the participants were highly respected and recognized.

Connecting cultural artefacts and school mathematics

Cultural artefacts represent the social and cultural knowledge and identity of the people of a particular community. Such cultural artefacts are rich in mathematical facts and principles and are source for mathematical concepts. Many mathematical ideas are embedded in those cultural artefacts. The result of this paper is based on the empirical research carried out in the course of my Ph.D. study. I had designed a lesson for the exploration of mathematical ideas outside the classroom with the collaboration of teacher participants. I had assumed the existence of the mathematical ideas beyond the four walls of the classroom and the students' mathematical competencies would be enhanced with the help of out-of-school mathematics.

After we reached the temple premises, we let the students observe the temple, monuments, and its surroundings. I asked the participant students to note down the geometrical objects and the probable mathematical concept that they could identify in and around the temple. After some time of observation, each group was requested to present their observations and findings. The students explored mathematical ideas embedded in different artefacts inside the temple premises. I observed that the students actively participated in the learning process. Each student was engaged in different activities in their ways. Some of them were taking data with measuring tools, while some were comparing those data to determine if they were symmetrical or not, and others them were using verification of different geometrical objects.

Each group involved in the common task serially presented their findings. The common observation made by the students were the 2D shapes of the objects like triangle, square, quadrilateral, circle, oval, octagon, trapezium, parallelogram, and rectangle embedded in the cultural artifacts. They also observed 3D shapes like hemisphere, cone, frustum, sphere, cube, cuboid, cylinder, prism, and pyramid. They sorted out the concepts of concentric circles, transformation, reflection, rotation, symmetry, pattern, and tessellations. The identification of concentric circles used to form such impressive artefacts also gives us a hint on how these mathematical ideas were created at that time which is far from today's formal studies based on bookish knowledge. Consistency and homogeneity are found in the construction of cultural artifacts. Therefore, we can see that the people used implicit mathematical ideas in such creations. Each artefact was precisely constructed resulting in the design of the artefacts. One artefact had a cuboid overlapped by other cuboids but of smaller size continuing till the top point was formed. It gave a shape like that of a pyramid. Also, there was an artefact with an octagon shape satisfying every property of a regular octagon.

Student participants also reported that the images that were carved in the doors, ceilings, windows, and other places were completely symmetrical. The artefacts which possessed bilateral symmetry seemed to have an axis of reflection which acted as a mirror giving the same image as the part which formed the complete view of those artefacts. The carving of different objects, in woods and stones were systematically carved. If observed with reference to any line, we get each part of the object that has the same reflected image. Every artefact that was considered to be a part of the symmetrical design was really attractive.

Image 1: Teacher assigning the task to students

One group of students was assigned a task to identify the center of the circular surface of the *Chaitya*. It possessed different geometrical shapes along with a circular face. The excitement in students was increasing. And probably, they were trying to figure out the mathematics present around the *Chaitya* itself as they were making an angle to angle view of it. This required physical materials like measuring tapes, ropes, markers, etc. which were provided to the group. They were left to accomplish of the task for about 15 minutes. Students were struggling to find the dimension of the circular surface of the *Chaitya*. They were trying to use a compass but this did not work out because of the larger size of the circular surface. Finally, they came to the teacher and said:

Image 2: Students engagement in the task

the teacher and said:

Student: Sir, we found out the center sir.

Teacher: Wow, what did you do children? Can you share that with me?

Students: yes sir!

Teacher: Please tell me the process.

Students: Sir, first we took a point in the circumference of the circle and put one end of the measuring tape in that point. Then, we loosely held the other side of the measuring tape and moved the tape along the circumference until we found the tightest point of the measuring tape. This probably was the longest chord, the diameter. Hence we marked the diameter and calculated the position of its midpoint. This is the center of that circular side.

Teacher: Wonderful! This is a great procedure, my children. I am really happy with you!

Student: Thank you, sir.

Image 3 depicted the procedures followed and the brief report presented by the student participants to solve the assignment given to them.

Image 3: Students' Presentation of the Assigned Task

Their report shows that they had used empirical knowledge to solve the mathematical problem of finding the center of the circle in the case of non-given other dimensions of a circle. As a researcher, I observed their presentation to their teacher facilitator. I observed their facial expressions which seemed to have a shining face, enjoying each step of their work. I also observed their behaviours. They were showing active participation and involvement in the task. All the students were involved as active participants in a group. Then I had a brief conversation with the students:

Researcher: Students, I appreciate your achievement!

Students: Thanks, sir!

Researcher: What did you learn today?

Students: Sir, we enjoyed today's practical work. We got that opportunity to work out the way that is not even in our textbook.

Researcher: For example.

Student: Sir we figured out the way of determining the center of a given circle in a way that is not mentioned in the textbook. You probably have noticed that in our presentation.

Researcher: Yes! Then what do you think about this project? Would it contribute to the learning of those textbook materials?

Student: No doubt about that. We internalized the mathematical concepts. We touched those mathematical ideas with our senses. We are never forgetting these learned items all our life.

Researcher: Thank you for your wonderful compliments.

Students: Especial thanks goes to you sir as you made all this provision.

I was really happy to see these students doing their tasks so eagerly. I could feel their excitement and enhanced facial expressions. The heterogeneous nature of the group involved in the task provided an opportunity to learn collaboratively. This framework provides an opportunity to learn mathematics concepts and ideas, even of a higher order, that are embedded in the cultural artefacts. The observation of cultural artefacts from a mathematical point of view contributed to the development of a positive attitude towards the subject. It also helped to elaborate mathematical concepts and develop knowledge to tackle non-routine problems.

The wonderful mathematical ideas and concepts were found in the observation of different artefacts. The mathematical ideas embedded in the out-of-school context and the pedagogy used in their cultural setting could be a powerful tool for the teaching and learning of school mathematics. The culture-friendly pedagogy provides students with the opportunity to explore the mathematical ideas embedded in different cultural arts and artifacts. Regarding the students' views on the ethnopädagogy, one of the student participants say:

It is our first trip of this kind. I had never imagined that mathematics could be learned without a textbook and worksheets beyond the classroom. We learned a lot of mathematical ideas and became able to explore mathematical ideas embedded in the cultural artifacts.

From the observation in the field and the interviews with the students, I found that ethnopädagogy is an effective approach for the teaching and learning of mathematics. This approach for teaching mathematics provided an opportunity to learn mathematical concepts embedded in the cultural arts and artifacts. This approach created an environment for the students to construct mathematical knowledge and develop ideas in their own ways. With this connection, other research participants said:

I never thought that mathematics can be learned without a textbook. With the observation of different cultural artefacts in the temple and its premises, we find different mathematics objects. We verified the mathematical facts and properties with the measuring instruments and calculating their dimensions. I learned different mathematical ideas with joyful moments and enjoyed a lot with this approach.

The constructivist framework was followed during different stages in my study. The students were given a rich learning environment and allowed to create their meaning by providing different tasks during teaching and learning through the use of ethnopädagogy. As my theoretical orientation about knowledge generation is based on the premise of a constructivist philosophy, the children construct mathematical knowledge as a result of active participation in their social context. In this vein, Vygotsky (1978) argued that cultural practices and resources mediate children in the process of development of thinking and can help them to learn school mathematics. Many things in the out-of-school environment can be connected to the teaching and learning of school mathematics. In my observation in the field, the study of different cultural artefacts plays a significant role in the teaching and learning of mathematics. The connection of students' familiar context in the process of teaching mathematical content provides a rich opportunity for the learners. The incorporation of an

ethnomathematical approach in the school mathematics classroom encourages students to learn and develop a positive attitude towards mathematics.

Concluding remarks

Mathematics is a pan-cultural phenomenon. Each culture has developed its mathematical system based on their everyday needs. There are lots of mathematical ideas present in the out-of-school environment if analyzed seriously. The observation of the cultural artefacts and the mathematical ideas embedded in those artefacts motivated and encouraged the students to explore more mathematics. They may also develop a positive attitude towards school mathematics. The study of mathematical ideas embedded in cultural artefacts helps to create ample opportunity to develop mathematical knowledge beyond the four walls of a classroom. The field-trip approach can be used as a pedagogical tool for the teaching and learning of mathematics. Their report shows that they had used empirical knowledge to solve the mathematical problem of finding the center of the circle in the case of non-given other dimensions of a circle. This approach provides students with the opportunity to learn mathematics in their own way and to develop mathematical ideas without the textbook and beyond the classroom. The collaborative learning framework involving heterogeneous group members from grades six to ten provides an opportunity to learn mathematics concepts, even at the higher level. Students from the junior classes also explored different mathematical ideas with the help of senior peers. It is concluded that students' knowledge construction ability requires apprenticeship into culturally specific cognitive and social practices.

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